

ETHICS REVIEW APPLICATION FORM

To be used for School or University level review

Please append all relevant and supporting documentation to this project application form when submitting for School level (SREC) or University (UREC) review. Text boxes will expand as required and all language used to explain or justify the application should be comprehensible to a lay person.

Application form and all associated documents should be submitted electronically.

Submission deadline dates for UREC can be found on the [UREC webpage](#).

Section 1: APPLICATION DETAILS

1.1 PROJECT AND DATES				
Title	Participatory workshops for co-creation of food product concept briefs (Part of Project FoodsEqual: Food systems for healthier food and a healthier planet)			
Date of submission	10/08/2022			
Start date	23/08/2022			
End date	30/06/2024			
1.2 APPLICANT DETAILS				
Chief Investigator	Professor Lisa Methven			
Please note that an undergraduate or postgraduate student cannot be a named Chief Investigator for research ethics purposes. The supervisor must be declared as Chief Investigator.				
Is the project being carried out in whole or in part to support a student degree?				
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Undergraduate <input type="checkbox"/> Masters <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PhD <input type="checkbox"/> No				
School	School of Chemistry, Food and Pharmacy			
Department	Department of Food and Nutritional Sciences (FNS)			
Email	l.methven@reading.ac.uk			
Telephone	+44 (0) 118 378 8714			
All other Applicants	Name:	School	Position	Email
	Rachel Smith	School of Chemistry, Food and Pharmacy	Postdoctoral Research Assistant	r.smith7@reading.ac.uk
	Sally Lloyd Evans	Archaeology, Geography and	Associate Professor	s.lloyd-evans@reading.ac.uk

		Environmental Science (SAGES)		
	Lorna Zischka	Archaeology, Geography and Environmental Science	Postdoctoral Research Assistant	Lorna.zischka@reading.ac.uk
	Trisha Bennett	External (WCDA)	Community Liaison Officer	cd@whitley-cda.org trisha.bennett@reading.ac.uk
	Raluca Briazu	School of Psychology	Research Fellow	r.briazu@reading.ac.uk
	Clare Pettinger	External (University of Plymouth)	Lecturer in Public Health Dietetics	clare.pettinger@plymouth.ac.uk
	Louise Hunt	External (University of Plymouth)	Postdoctoral Research Assistant	louise.hunt@plymouth.ac.uk
	Lisa Howard	External (University of Plymouth)	Community Research Coordinator	lisa.howard@plymouth.ac.uk
	Hannah Gardiner	External (University of Plymouth)	PhD Student	hannah.gardiner@plymouth.ac.uk
	Elaine Swan	External (University of Sussex)	Senior Lecturer in Human Resources and Organisational Behaviour	E.Swan@sussex.ac.uk
	Jesse Hsu	External (University of Sussex)	Postdoctoral Research Assistant	j.hsu@sussex.ac.uk
	Shelley Taylor	External (Brighton & Hove Food Partnership)	Development Manager	shelley@bhfood.org.uk
	Sonia Duval	Archaeology, Geography and Environmental Science	Community Research Assistant	s.duval@reading.ac.uk
	Rosie Tsikritzi	School of Chemistry, Food and Pharmacy	Postdoctoral Research Assistant	r.tsikritzi@reading.ac.uk

1.3 WHAT REVIEW IS NEEDED?

Please tick the appropriate box below to confirm which review your ethics application requires.

Please tick all that apply.

School Level Review and Approval (SREC)

External (for example, HRA)

<input type="checkbox"/> University Research Ethics Committee Review (UREC)	
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Projects expected to require review by the University Research Ethics Committee (for example; research involving NHS patients, research involving potential for distress to participants) must be reviewed by the Chair of the School Ethics Committee or the Head of School before submission to UREC. For further information see Section 16 of the [UREC Guidance](#).

1.4 EXTERNAL RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEES

Please provide details of other external research ethics committees from whom a favourable ethics opinion will be required (for example; HRA REC)

Name of Committee	Date of submission / approval	Reference	Status
Click here to enter text.	Click here to enter a date.	Click here to enter text.	Click here to enter text.

1.5 PROJECT SUBMISSION DECLARATION

On behalf of my co-applicants and myself,

- I confirm that to the best of my knowledge I have made known all information relevant to the appropriate Research Ethics Committee and I undertake to inform the Committee(s) of any such information which subsequently becomes available whether before or after the research has begun
- I understand that it is a legal requirement that both staff and students undergo Disclosure and Barring Service checks when in a position of trust (for example; when working with children or vulnerable adults)
- I confirm that if this project is an intervention study, a list of names and contact details of the participants in this project will be compiled and that this, together with a copy of the Consent Form, will be retained within the School for as long as necessary.
- I confirm that I have given due consideration to equality and diversity in the management, design and conduct of the research project.
- (For Chemistry, Food & Pharmacy (CFP) only) I confirm the Internal Review has been undertaken by [Click here to enter text.](#) and I have made the changes requested.

SIGNED, CHIEF INVESTIGATOR

25/01/2023

Where required by the School's Research Ethics Procedures, this ethics application should be signed off by the appropriate person to confirm the School Body are content for this application to be reviewed by UREC.

Chemistry, Food & Pharmacy – will require sign off from: Chair of SREC, Head of Department and School Ethics Administrator – insert rows below as required.

SIGNED, AUTHORISING SIGNATORY

Signature:	Position:	Date:
	Head of Department	Click here to enter a date.
	Choose an item.	Click here to enter a date.
	Choose an item.	Click here to enter a date.

	Choose an item.	Click here to enter a date.
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Section 2: PROJECT DETAILS

2.1 LAY SUMMARY

Please provide a summary of the project in plain English that can be understood by a non-specialist audience, which includes a description of the background of the study (existing knowledge), the questions the project will address, the methods to be used and the key ethical issues.

Please note the lay summary should not contain references and be no more than 500 words.

This project is part of a bigger research proposal that is running over five years ('FoodSEqual' 2021-2026) and seeks to provide people living in disadvantaged communities with improved access to fresher food and a balance of desirable, sustainable, affordable and 'healthy' products. The communities involved in this project are geographically located in Reading, Tower Hamlets, Plymouth and Brighton & Hove.

Overall, the project focuses on giving a voice and power to those who are often left behind when food systems, food policies and novel products are designed. This project seeks to collaborate with people from so called 'disadvantaged communities', co-producing ways in which everyone can access a desirable and affordable diet that meets our health needs whilst minimising wastage and protecting our planet.

As a next step on from our 'shopping basket task' which helped us to understand what people currently eat, and what changes, if any, they would like to make to their diet, we aim to run further workshops to explore the specific food categories identified in the previous task. The insights from these focus groups aim to inform priorities for new product development and policy changes for foods that benefit the communities in the most helpful direction of change.

In these workshops we will bring representatives from within communities, and a small number of industry partners and academic researchers together to co-create product concept briefs. (Note: SREC approval for previous Reading workshops was obtained through SAGES with Professor Sally Lloyd-Evans as PI in collaboration with the FNS team. However, this new application is for the product concept development stage of the project and is broader than the Reading (Whitley) community. We are applying to SCFP SREC in order that the FNS team will be able to help facilitate these concept workshops in Plymouth, Brighton & Hove and Tower Hamlets, as well as in Whitley Reading).

2.2 PRIMARY RESEARCH QUESTION

Please detail the primary research question this project will answer.

To define concept briefs: What characteristics of food products are wanted to provide communities better access to healthy, desirable, sustainable, and affordable foods?

Note: the food products (product categories and / or eating occasions) under investigation initially resulted from earlier workshops with the same geographic communities (eg the "shopping basket" task mentioned in section 2.1).

2.3 SECONDARY RESEARCH QUESTION(S)

Please detail any secondary research question(s) this project will answer.

- What are typical contexts that people eat specific foods in, Or want to eat these foods in?
- What are the factors that lead to their consumption? Are there factors that lead to a food not being able to be consumed (ie barriers)?
- What roles do these foods play in people's lives and what are the rewards/barriers/aspirations about eating them?
- What might alternatives look like and what characteristics must they have to be liked and chosen?
- What does a specific food(s) need to provide and are there any underpinning aspirations to replace a specific current food(s) with healthier / less junk food / tastier / affordable / more sustainable alternatives.

Note (as in 2.2): the specific food products / categories of foods under investigation initially resulted from earlier workshops with the same geographic communities (eg the "shopping basket" task mentioned in section 2.1).

2.4 DESIGN AND PROCEDURE

Please describe concisely what the study will involve, how many times and in what order, for your participants and the procedures and methodology to be used.

Note: Any questionnaires or interview scripts should be appended to this application.

We propose to run 3-5 workshops in each community with a maximum of 6-8 participants per group.

- The workshops will be conducted face to face where appropriate in booked rooms for privacy. When applicable, current Covid-19 guidelines will be followed at all times (this would include face mask wearing, social distancing and sanitisation of the shared spaces and materials as required under guidelines at the time of the workshop).
- The workshop questions and activities are currently being co-produced with the other academic institutions, community researchers, community members and organisations who are partnered with the FoodSEquals project. As such, the exact protocol is subject to change, although it is anticipated these will be minor from an ethics perspective. The generic protocol of this task is in Appendix 2 and a more specific food example that will be used in Whitley is in Appendix 3. The exact questions will vary depending on the flow of the conversation within different workshops and different communities, and so are only suggested as prompts.
- The protocol has 3 key stages:
 - o Storyboarding to determine the use or the identified foods within a day or week and rewards and barriers to its use.
 - o Exploration of current food(s) on the market that fit the defined food type or category under investigation
 - o Co-creation of the product concept brief by understanding the valuable attributes a food should have

Once the initial product concept brief has been developed, we will re-contact participants where needed via the community researchers to continue to ensure it matches their expectations, to edit it and fill in any gaps that were not possible to complete within the workshops. This will be done via short questionnaires (Appendix 4) that include the important attributes identified in the workshops and some potential product concepts put forward using the insights from the workshops. Participants will be shown a product concept and asked to

rate it against attributes that were identified as important such as filling, healthy, tasty etc. This opportunity will also be extended to those who did not take part in the initial workshops.

2.5 LOCATION

Please describe where the research will take place.

These workshops will be run in each geographic community in either privately booked rooms or rooms belonging to the community. In Reading, the workshops will be held in the Whitley Community Café.

Please state whether an appropriate risk assessment/ local review has been undertaken.

- Yes
 No
 Not required

Note:

- Ensure specific risk assessments have been undertaken for non-University locations (for example; schools or participant homes). Please consult either your School Ethics Contact or UREC for guidance.

If the project is to take place in Hugh Sinclair Unit of Human Nutrition, it must be reviewed by the Research Nurses and the Hugh Sinclair Manager also informed that the ethics application is being submitted for the study.' Signatures are required below.

	Hugh Sinclair Manager	Click here to enter a date.
	Research Nurse <i>Click here to enter text.</i>	Click here to enter a date.

2.6 FUNDING

Is the research supported by funding from a research council or other external source (for example; charities, businesses)?

- Yes
 No

If "yes", please,

(a) Give details of the funding body;

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF)

(b) Confirm if the funder specifically stipulates review by the University Research Ethics Committee.

- Yes
 No

2.7 ETHICAL ISSUES

Please summarise the main ethical issues, including harms and risks, arising from your study and explain how you have addressed them.

Food can be an emotional subject so we appreciate that some participants may have difficult experiences that they want to share. The researchers will seek to avoid explicitly eliciting information about traumatic experiences and will remain sensitive to signs of distress. If appropriate, information will be offered to participants about accessing support services or advice from local organisations. We are collaborating with trusted charities and community organisations that will be able to provide further advice and support.

We will have food samples available during workshops and, therefore, all allergens will be highlighted at each workshop to ensure no-one tastes a food that might put them at risk of an allergic or intolerance reaction.

2.8 DECEPTION

Will the research involve any element of intentional deception (for example; providing false or misleading information about the study)?

- Yes
 No

If "yes", please justify and append a description of the debriefing procedure.

Click here to enter text.

2.9 PAYMENT

Will research participants receive any payments, reimbursement of expenses or any other benefits or incentives for taking part in this research?

- Yes
 No

If "yes", please specify and justify the amount.

Participants will receive a £20 voucher as reimbursement for taking part in the study. Participants who take part in the questionnaire that we return to the community with will receive a £10 voucher as reimbursement for taking part.

2.10 DATA PROTECTION

This section is required for applications reviewed at School (SREC) level only.

For applications reviewed at UREC level, do not complete this section. Move onto section 2.11.

What steps will be taken to ensure appropriate secure handling of personal data? Give comprehensive details on the collection, retention, sharing and disposal of participant personal data.

Personal data means any data relating to a participant who could potentially be identified. It includes pseudonymised data capable of being linked to a participant through a unique code number.

For guidance on data protection please, see the [Data Protection for Researchers Guidance](#) document.

The workshops will be audio recorded with participant permission and photographs will be taken of the storyboard and other creative material after they have been produced by the participants (and the participants will not be in those images). Any images of participants (that have provided consent for images) will not be stored with other data or personal identification data but may be shared on social media or in presentations about the project.

Materials from each geographic community will be saved as docx, Excel, JPEG or MP3/ WAV files, de-identified and stored securely on a shared collaborative drive hosted by individual universities: the University of Reading, the University of Sussex and the University of Plymouth. All data collected will be digitised and stored in electronic file format and stored on servers which have automated backup and password protection.

For the Whitley community workshops, we will use a University of Reading collaborative files share as our primary storage, accessible to the project investigators and community researchers, and Microsoft Teams for sharing anonymised data with external partners and organisations. Any non-digital paperwork will be transferred to digital form and then shredded. All data will be stored and shared in accordance with the University of Reading Data Protection Policy.

2.11 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Requirement for applications to be submitted to UREC, only.

Applications submitted to UREC must be accompanied by a [Data Management Plan](#) (document available via link).

Please append the Data Management Plan.

- N/A, application not to be submitted to UREC
 Yes, appended*

*Please note; as the Data Management Plan is appended there is **no** requirement to complete section 2.10 Data Protection.

2.12 DATA PROTECTION IMPACT ASSESSMENT (DPIA)

Will the research involve any activity that requires a [Data Protection Impact Assessment](#) (DPIA)?

- Yes
 No

If "yes", please append the "[Pre-Screening Questionnaire for Data Protection Impact Assessment](#)".

Please note; the Pre-Screening Questionnaire for a DPIA is only accessible with staff credentials and the Chief Investigator is responsible for its completion.

2.13 INFORMED CONSENT

a. Will you obtain informed consent from, or on behalf of, research participants?

- Yes (go to question b)
 No (go to question c)

b. If "yes", please describe the process by which they will be informed about the nature of the study and the process by which you will obtain consent.

c. If "no", you are not obtaining consent, please explain why (for example; 'opt-out' methodology without the acquisition of consent)?

Please append all relevant participant facing information documentation for participants, parents or guardians. Please note, age-appropriate information sheets must be supplied for all participants wherever possible, including children. Assent should be obtained from children, under 16 years, in addition to the consent required from parents, guardians or carers.

Potential participants will be provided with a Participant Information Sheet (Appendix 1) and will be asked to provide written and verbal consent before the workshops start (recorded on a Consent Form in Appendix 1). Appendix 1 informs participants that they can withdraw from the study at any time, without giving a reason and they will be reminded verbally of this at the start of the focus group. Appendix 1 can be amended to include the relevant details for each community.

2.14 GENOTYPING

Are you intending to genotype the participants?

- Yes
 No

If "yes", which genotypes will be determined?

2.15 TISSUE SAMPLE MANAGEMENT

What types of human tissue or other biological material will be included in this study?

- HTA relevant
 Non-HTA relevant
 None

Please provide additional details here

Will the HTA relevant samples be stored for longer than 7 days?

- Yes
 No

How long will the samples be stored for?

____ Years ____ Months

What will happen to the samples at the end of the research?

- Retention
 Disposal
 Transfer

Please provide additional details here if applicable

NB: If HTA relevant samples are to be collected and stored by researchers in FNS the ethics application must be reviewed and signed by the Designated Individual for the Human Tissue Act (2004) licence

SIGNED, AUTHORISING SIGNATORY

Signature:

Position:

Date:

Choose an item.

Click here to enter a date.

Section 3: PARTICIPANT DETAILS

3.1 PARTICIPANT NUMBER

How many participants do you plan to recruit?

Please briefly explain why the number is appropriate to answer the study's research question(s).

We plan to recruit for 3-5 workshops of 6-8 people. This is considered an appropriate number of participants and groups for an exploratory qualitative method. These workshops will consist of 4 or 5 community members, 1 university researcher, 1 or 2 community researchers, 1 or 2 industry representatives with an interest in the chosen food area.

3.2 PARTICIPANT CHARACTERISATION

What age-range of participants will you recruit?

We will recruit participants over the age of 18.

Please list the principal inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Participants will be included if they are:

Over the age of 18 years

And are a member/user or volunteer of Whitley community café (or the other relevant partnerships with the other universities)

Participants will be excluded if they are:

Under the age of 18

And are not a member/user or volunteer of Whitley community café (or the other relevant partnerships with the other universities)

3.3 RECRUITMENT

Please describe the recruitment process and append any advertising if used.

Workshop participants (aged 18+ only) will be recruited through our established partnerships with the community and through our industry partners who are on the project. They will attend to considerations around generation, gender and ethnicity. Participants will be able to draw on their personal and community contacts for participation (bring a friend) if they wish.

Industry participants will be contacted via the project via email, and community participants will be recruited via word of mouth. Interested potential participants will be given a Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form (Appendix 1).

3.4 NHS AND SOCIAL SERVICES INVOLVEMENT

Will participants be recruited because of their status as NHS patients or Social Services clients, or identified through those services' records?

Yes

No

If "yes", please give details of current status of the HRA REC review.

Click here to enter text.

<p>Will the study involve adult participants unable to consent for themselves as defined by the Mental Capacity Act 2005 or other vulnerable adults?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If "yes", please detail the associated procedures as set out in the HRA REC application.</p> <p><i>Click here to enter text.</i></p>
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CHECKLIST

1. The Application form has the appropriate signatories		Yes
2. The Participant Information Sheet includes a statement to the effect that the project has been reviewed by the appropriate Research Ethics Committee and has been given a favourable ethical opinion for conduct.		Yes
3. The Participant Information Sheet contains the relevant Data Protection information.		Yes
4. Where minors (under 18) and vulnerable adults are involved in the study/research, please confirm that all investigators have obtained a full enhanced DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service check). Please select 'Not applicable' if this does not apply to your research.		Not Applicable
5. EITHER	a) The proposed research will not generate any information about the health of participants;	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
OR	b) If the research could reveal adverse information regarding the health of participants, their consent to pass information on to their GP will be included in the consent form and in this circumstance I will inform the participant and their GP, providing a copy of the relevant details to each and identifying by date of birth.	<input type="checkbox"/>
OR	c) I have explained within the application why (b) above is not appropriate.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. EITHER	a) The proposed research does not involve children under the age of 5;	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
OR	b) My Head of School (or authorised responsible person) has given details of the proposed research to the <u>University's insurance officer</u> .	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. EITHER	a) The proposed research does not involve the taking of blood samples:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
OR	b) For anyone whose proximity to the blood samples brings a risk of Hepatitis B, documentary evidence of immunity prior to the risk of exposure will be retained by the Head of School or authorised responsible person.	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. EITHER	a) The proposed research does not involve the storage of human tissue, as defined by the <u>Human Tissue Act 2004</u> ;	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
OR	b) I have explained within the application how the requirements of the Human Tissue Act 2004 will be met.	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. EITHER	a) The proposed research does not involve the use of ionising radiation;	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
OR	b) I am aware the proposed research will require <u>HRA REC review</u> .	<input type="checkbox"/>

VERSION CONTROL

VERSION	KEEPER	REVIEWED	APPROVED BY	APPROVAL DATE
1.5	UREC	Annually	UREC	September 2021
1.6	UREC	Annually	UREC	February 2022